

EPIC Immune Cell Fractions (Z-score)

Immune Cell Infiltration by Tumor Histology

PCA of Immune Cell Fractions

Supplementary Figure Captions

Supplementary Figure S1.

Heatmap of immune cell fractions (row-wise z-score) estimated by EPIC. Tumour and normal samples show clear clustering separation, primarily driven by differences in CD4⁺ and CD8⁺T cell abundance.

Supplementary Figure S2.

Boxplot of estimated immune cell proportions across different histological subtypes (normal, atypia, carcinoma in situ, carcinoma). CD4⁺T cell levels are consistently lower in tumour subtypes.

Supplementary Figure S3.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of immune cell fractions estimated by EPIC. PC1 differentiates tumour and normal tissues based on immune profile composition.